

Sustainable Design Issues in Sincerity Expression: With the Case of Gift-Wrapping

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Abstract: People often sacrifice themselves for sustainability, but they do not often consider sustainability when serving others to express sincerity. In this study we focus on the activity of gift-wrapping¹, as an important social behavior that creates notable waste. The purpose of this research is to investigate the general approach to gift-giving and gift-wrapping regarding sustainability, and how it might be possible to embody sustainability without degrading sincerity. A focus group and generative workshop were conducted respectively, and insights from the focus group were used when setting up the generative workshop. Through this study, we found that emotional value cannot be compromised by sustainability when expressing sincerity in gift-wrapping. Gift givers do not want to forfeit any sincerity by using eco-friendly materials that could be seen as inappropriate to the recipient. However, from the generative workshop, we found that people can show their true intentions by incorporating messages, by using conservable products that are reusable in other situations, by adding visual aesthetics, and by adding surprise aspects. This result shows that we can creatively adapt sustainability while keeping our emotional values.

Key words: *Sustainability, Sincerity, Generative design*

1. Introduction

In Northeast Asian countries like Korea, Japan and China, courtesy is one of the most important cultural values. courtesy becomes more important when people want to express their affection or respect to others. Therefore, showing sincerity really matters when serving guests or giving something to someone for appreciation or celebration. Even though this is a common attitude as a social behavior, the method of showing sincerity often goes against the promotion of sustainability because this behavior produces waste in most situations. For

¹ In this study, we differentiate the term 'gift-wrapping' from 'packaging'. It focuses on the additional decoration which can be even wrapped over the packages.

instance, when a host cooks dinner for guests, preparing more dishes than usual is considered a sincere behavior. When submitting documents to a senior-level person, printing on fresh high quality paper and using a formal envelop is required to be courteous. Sincerity is commonly expressed in the way of ‘the more, the better.’ Consequently, this behavior results in a lot of waste.

This social behavior occurs when people exchange gifts: It is one of the ways in which we can transmit to others the images we have of them in our minds [4]. Hence, people make a great effort to demonstrate their sincerity not only in the gift itself but also in the wrapping materials. Actually Japanese have always considered it discourteous simply to pass an unwrapped, unconcealed object from one hand to another [1]. Although the wrapping of gifts plays the role of heightening the recipient’s surprise [3] and has a favorable influence on attitudes toward owning what is received [2], it has been criticized for generating *unnecessary* waste. In fact, six million tons of waste are generated by gift-wrapping every year in South Korea [5]. However, Koreans cannot easily adopt ways that may make them seem insincere in order to consider sustainability, which might generally be considered ‘the less, the better.’ Because this conflict between emotional factors and sustainability has not been clearly solved yet, current solutions are not widely accepted by the public.

To solve this problem, designers can play a significant role because designers are the ones who offer the materials to users for expressing their sincerity. In gift-wrapping, designers can decide what kind of materials should be used to produce wrapping paper, suggest a new technique to wrap gifts or even offer a new kit for gift-wrapping. Therefore, we wanted to examine from the designer’s point of view the relationship between emotional factors and sustainability, which seem conflicting in the context of showing sincerity so that designers could propose more sustainable ways. To study this, we first conducted a focus group to brainstorm general ideas of the emotional factors and environmental concerns in gift-wrapping. With the rationales based on the results from the focus group, we set a generative design workshop to extract important qualities of optimized substitutes for gift-wrapping concerning sustainability through participants’ creativity. As a result of these two studies, we introduce some critical qualities which should be implemented to create new substitutes that can retain emotional value and be more eco-friendly as well.

2. Emotional Factors and Environmental Concerns in Gift-wrapping

We conducted a focus group to understand the general ideas of gift-wrapping and environmental concerns in gift-wrapping for the rationales used when selecting materials and recruiting participants of the generative workshop. Two main topics we wanted to explore are i) what qualities are critical in gift-wrapping and how participants express them, and ii) what wrappers would be specifically concerned about regarding sustainability when wrapping a gift.

2.1. Setup of the Focus Group

Participants

Four students with notable gift exchange experience were recruited to participate in the focus group (2 males and 2 females). All subjects, in their twenties, were chosen because they had had opportunities to give gifts not

only to those who had a higher social status but also people of the same or lower.

Procedure

The study lasted one hour and consisted of three sessions: i) sharing their experiences and ideas of general gift-wrapping behavior, ii) discussion about various gift-wrapping examples we prepared, and iii) discussion about environmental concerns in gift-wrapping. The gift-wrapping examples were presented as pictures which showed various examples from normal gift wrapping to eco-friendly gift wrapping (figure 1). Eco-friendly gift wrapping examples included gifts wrapped with natural materials, recycled and reduced material, and reusable materials like boxes and fabric.

Figure 1. Focus group (left) and provided gift-wrapping examples (right)

2.2. Analysis

We extracted notable concepts of emotional factors and environmental concerns in gift-wrapping from the results of the focus group.

Sincerity may easily contradict environmental concerns

The most important quality of gift-wrapping is showing the giver's sincerity toward the recipient. Even though givers may think wrapping does not have to be fancy, they believe it must represent their sincerity in some way. It can be demonstrated in many other ways than making it fancy, such as writing a card. However, in terms of environmental concerns, they felt very negative about having to be intentionally eco-friendly since they believed it could significantly degrade their sincerity. Besides that, one participant said, "*I would not feel happy if I found out the wrapping material was reused.*" Since they considered being eco-friendly as reduction and reuse, they asserted it should not be taken into account when giving gifts with gratitude. Although they stated that they often reused boxes and shopping bags as wrapping materials, it was not because of environmental concerns but for their usefulness. In the case of kraft paper which is usually made of environmentally friendly material, it was preferred because it goes well with any contents and they can decorate it themselves with no regard for environmental concerns.

Harmonizing the wrapping design with its recipient and the gift content matters.

Some eco-friendly wrapping materials were preferred, such as kraft paper (recycled) and Bojagi (Korean traditional wrapping cloth which is reusable), but they imposed the constraint that it should harmonize with the

recipient and the gift content. Even though the subjects answered that they would like to use kraft paper as wrapping material, they said that it would not be proper for recipients who were of a higher social status. Also, one male participant sarcastically exclaimed, “*Who would wrap a ring box with Bojagi? It would look so old-fashioned.*” This result demonstrates that matching the wrapping material to the recipient and the gift content is an important matter.

Aesthetics in gift-wrapping cannot be compromised for environmental issues.

A visually pleasing appearance is also a critical factor when selecting wrapping materials. If it looks nice when wrapped, participants said they would be willing to use it. When we presented many pictures of gift-wrapping options during the second session, colorful recycled paper was the most popular wrapping material but a cloth made of hemp was considered highly negative. Even when using kraft paper, the subjects wanted additional decorations such as stamps or ribbons on it so that it would not look too simple. One female participant asserted, “*A flower bouquet does not need more than one ribbon as it looks beautiful as it is.*”

3. Optimizing Emotion and Sustainability in Gift-wrapping

A generative workshop was conducted based on the insights from the focus group. The purpose of the generative workshop was to answer deeper and more specific questions with respect to each insight from the focus group: i) how users (i.e., gift-wrappers) react to eco-friendliness in gift-wrapping, ii) how users differentiate gift-wrapping according to the gift content and its recipient in terms of environmental impact, iii) what kinds of materials are acceptable to users – without degrading their emotional value, and iv) how users can embody eco-friendliness in gift-wrapping while keeping sincerity. In the generative workshop, users were mainly asked to wrap gifts with materials we provided.

3.1. Setup of the Generative Workshop

Participants

Four students in their 20s participated in the generative workshop (2 males and 2 females). The subjects, whose ages ranged from 24 to 28 years old, had numerous experiences of gift-wrapping and claimed to enjoy it. We intentionally excluded the participants of the focus group as the subjects for the generative workshop because we did not want the first session of the workshop to be influenced by the idea of environment conservation. Therefore, the participants of the focus group were not suitable, because they had already been exposed to the main idea of this research through discussions in the focus group.

Gift-wrapping Material Selection

Firstly, four kinds of gift-contents – a wallet, a diary, a mug and a package of tea – were chosen (figure 2), because the participants of the focus group had said that the wrapping is mainly affected by the external characteristics of the gift itself. Both wallets (a) and cups (c) are not rectangular, but wallets are soft and cups are solid. Diaries (b) and tea bag boxes (d) are both rectangular, but tea bag boxes are differentiated because they are already packed in good-looking boxes. It was expected from answers in the focus group that the tea bag boxes (d) would be wrapped with minimum materials because of aesthetic patterns on the box. To determine the

influence of social status, two pieces were prepared for each type of gift.

Figure 2. Products to be wrapped

The wrapping materials were selected carefully to give users a variety of choices. As the main surface wrapping materials, diverse materials were prepared in terms of their eco-friendliness (figure 3). Used materials such as newspapers, magazines and fabric cloth were selected as the most eco-friendly materials. Kraft paper and Hanji (Korean traditional eco-friendly paper) were also prepared as eco-friendly materials. Boxes and, paper bags were given as semi eco-friendly materials. Common gift-wrapping papers and vinyl wrap were prepared. Decorative materials (figure 4) were also prepared such as flowers, colored ribbons, tags, stickers, cushioning materials and drawing tools. Basic tools for wrapping were provided such as tapes, double-sided tapes, glues, scissors and cutters.

Figure 3. Main wrapping materials

Figure 4. Decorative materials

Generative Workshop Procedure

The subjects started the workshop with selecting the gift content randomly. Each user was asked to select one box out of four big boxes containing each type of gifts. After choosing boxes, the workshop facilitator explained each material, and two 30-minute wrapping sessions followed. The task for the first wrapping session was to wrap two gifts as they would like to give or receive, but one gift was for a close friend and the other was for a respected person who has a higher social status than the user, for example teachers, parents or seniors. They could use any material provided and they were freely interviewed while and after wrapping. The second wrapping session had basically the same process as the first session, but the users were asked to wrap the same gifts in an eco-friendly way this time.

3.2. Analysis

The result was analyzed qualitatively. All the gift wrapping (figure 5) and interview results were gathered and analyzed. Each participant (A, B, C and D) wrapped 4 times during the whole generative workshop.

Figure 5. Gift-wrapping results

3.2.1. Attitude to eco-friendliness in gift-wrapping

The participants all agreed that sustainability was not and should not be the main concern of gift wrapping. This corresponds to the result of the focus group. For example, they used kraft paper a lot (7 out of 16 wrappings) not

because they considered sustainability, but because of the quality of the paper. As gift giving is for expressing gratitude or celebration to others, intentional sustainable wrapping is regarded as inappropriate. They said, *“If my friend gives me a gift wrapped in a recycled material or marked that this is eco-conscious wrapping, I would not feel good because it seems to be pushing me to live an environmentally friendly life.”* This comment shows that they do not want their pure sincerity to be degraded because of the bad wrapping. However, they also said, *“I was satisfied when my gift wrap happened to be eco-friendly.”* One of the participants (C) – who had experienced wrapping with a piece of magazine – said *“I was happy because it looked nice and was also eco-friendly, although I did not intend it.”*

3.2.2. Differences in eco-friendliness in terms of recipients and contents

From the results of the gift-wrapping (figure 5), several characteristics were found according to the recipients and the contents of the present. It was observed that participants wrapped their gifts in more creative ways for their friends than for a teacher or a senior. Gifts for a person who is of a higher social status (A2, B2, C2, D2, A4, B4, C4 and D4 in figure 5) were neat and tidy with simple surface materials. Two of them (B2 and D2) were wrapped in Korean style using Hanji and paper with conventional patterns and color. It is a common wrapping style for seniors in Korean society and seems that they wanted to keep the stereotype of gift-wrapping. They also tended to keep this stereotype when they were asked to wrap it in eco-friendly way. They just changed the type of paper into kraft paper (which is well known as eco-friendly material) but used a similar approach to wrapping.

However, for close friends, they tended to think more freely which made it made possible to generate new practical types of eco-friendly gift-wrapping. They considered a new way of tearing the wrapping (B1) and a layered style (C1 is made of magazine wrapped inside and punched Hanji outside). For the eco-friendly wrapping, they used a reusable paper bag (A3) and magazine paper (B3 and C3). The wrapping of B3 was designed as a book cover so that the recipient had the option to keep and use it. One participant firstly wanted to decorate the box (C3) with stamps and markers, but he wrapped it again because he did not like it. D3 was wrapped with magazines and fabric. He explained that he might have used any fabric at home.

Figure 6. Color match between gift and wrapped paper

They were all very concerned about the external characteristics of the contents. Regardless of the shape, they preferred rectangular shape and wanted to use a box if available. It was observed that they spent a long time selecting materials whose colors were well-matched to the contents. When gifts were opened after finishing the

wrapping, it was also found that the participants used similarly colored materials (figure 6).

3.2.3. Gift-wrapping technique for eco-friendliness

The most important factor in eco-friendly gift wrapping is not losing its emotional value in spite of a different set of materials. This generative workshop revealed that people express their sincerity for eco-friendly wrapping in a different way from normal wrapping. When they wrap their gifts without any attempt to be eco-friendly, they tend to use a lot of material to show their sincerity. As shown in figure 5 (C1, C2, D1 and C2), they normally wrap the whole surface of the gift with tape, tie it up with ribbons, attach a sticker, and put it into a paper bag. The process of opening such a gift has 3 or 4 steps, and it gives the recipient more entertainment. When the participants were asked to be eco-friendly, they embodied these surprise steps differently. For example when wrapping a wallet (figure 7), the participant put a thank you card inside the wallet so that recipient could have fun and see their sincerity without having the whole surface wrapped. This strategy is one of the *material reduction* techniques, but it still shows the giver's good faith.

Figure 7. Eco-friendly gift-wrapping example which contains a surprise element

As shown in figure 5 (A3, B3 and D3), we can wrap a gift with *reusable materials*. Paper bag (A3), book cover (B3) and simple fabric (D3) can be used by themselves. Boxes in good shape were preferred for reuse. Subjects also utilized *used material* which had other purposes such as magazines. Using *natural and recycled material* such as flowers and kraft paper is a simple way to be eco-friendly.

Another creative technique was *wrapping without gluing*. (A3, B3, B4 and D3) Participants did not use any or just minimal tape and glue, and instead tied the present up with paper ribbon.

Figure 8. Eco-friendly gift-wrapping example without gluing or taping

3.2.4. Eco-friendly material selection

Users avoided newspapers as a gift-wrapping material. They say “*Eco-friendly gift-wrapping should be differentiated from reuse-friendly wrapping.*” They worried that the newspapers used for gift-wrapping would make recipients misunderstand the giver’s sincerity as if they wanted to decrease the wrapping cost. Users got a negative image from eco-friendly materials because “*general eco-friendliness sometimes means ‘reusing’ itself.*” They thought it would be okay to receive this material themselves, but would rather not give it to others. They have positive feelings for kraft paper, as they think it looks trendy and gives a warm feeling. They said they would use recycled paper more if there were more variety of thicknesses, colors and qualities available. Natural material such as leaves and flowers are positively acceptable for wrapping. However, they are not practical because they shrivel up or gifts may get discolored by them. Participants liked materials that can be used afterwards, such as boxes, paper bags and scarves. They regarded these wrapping materials as another gift to be used for the recipient’s own needs.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

We have argued that a sustainable substitute for the way of showing sincerity suggests four key qualities. One is *its self-expressive value*. Sincerity can be demonstrated not only by fancy materials but also by the effort, such as writing a card or drawing a picture. Therefore, the substitute should be able to be customized. In this way, the gift would be more special since it is unique to that recipient and transmits the giver’s intention better. Another quality is to be *reusable but physically-conservable*. Even if it is reused, no one wants to reveal the fact. Hence, to implement this quality, it should keep the original shape as if it were new. The next quality is *visual aesthetics*. Users’ primary concern is how the result looks. If they cannot appreciate the appearance of their gift, they would not adapt to the new method. The last quality we identified is the *surprise* factor when the gift is presented. Most users conceal the content to make the recipient surprised, but surprise can be achieved in other ways like hiding a memo inside the gift content. Since surprise is one of the key emotions involved in a successful gift exchange, the *surprise* factor is critical.

In this gift-giving context, since gifts transmit the pictures of givers in recipients’ minds, the first quality ‘self-expressive value’ has significant potential. We found that it can be implemented more effectively through the giver’s creativity when the recipient is a close friend because in Korean culture, being courteous and neat toward a senior-level person is a more important social behavior than showing creativity. However, we expect this quality may have more potential in Western culture because relationships there are less hierarchical than in Korean tradition.

Based on these results, there are three ways designers can have significant influence on this situation. First, designers can suggest new gift-wrapping materials based on bio-degradable ingredients. We found covering the surface is a critical factor for emotional satisfaction of the wrapper. Therefore, using bio-degradable material is more desirable than reducing the quantity of used material. Second, a new eco-friendly wrapping method or kit can be developed by designers to cause people to behave eco-friendly unintentionally, without any extra effort or consideration on their part. Third, gift-wrapping services can be innovated by designers on a corporate

level. This could also act as a good opportunity to introduce and popularize a new public perception of eco-friendly gift-wrapping. For the strongest results, these three areas should be targeted together in an integrated effort to shift people's wrapping habits and expectations.

We found benefits and limitations through our research methodology. By conducting two types of experiments – a focus group and a generative workshop - we obtained deeper insights from the results of the generative workshop because we set it up to respond to the findings of the focus group. Moreover, the generative workshop gave us an opportunity to verify some insights we obtained from the focus group. However, the participants might have been influenced by the materials provided. During the generative workshop, we observed one of the participants felt like adding more decorations because of the various materials available. Thus, this practice may have resulted in more decorative gift-wrapping than would have been done in a typical case. We expect that we could get more concrete and interesting insights if we observed users in real gift-giving situations using materials they selected themselves. Another limitation of this method is that the proposed qualities may not include all possibilities, because we conducted the research with only four participants. We might have gotten more creative qualities for eco-friendly wrapping if the same study had been conducted with more participants. We also suppose that interviewing experts on gift-wrapping could provide meaningful insights for exploring further ideas.

From a broader point of view, we can find various other emotional values that conflict with sustainability; for instance, leaving a computer plugged in while not using it due to an inherent laziness, feeling unwilling to use second hand products and being thrilled by speeding a car. As design provides creative solutions by studying users' emotions on an experiential level, we expect that designers can play a significant role in solving these problems. In this study, we revealed that some emotional values cannot be compromised by sustainability through the case of sincerity but we tried to explore solutions which satisfy the two conflicting values in a reasonable fashion. This shows the possibility of discovering better ideas to make this world greener.

5. Acknowledgments

Thanks to Prof. Woo-hun Lee, Prof. Myung-suk Kim, Prof. Tek-Jin Nam, Mark Whiting and participants for input on this work.

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